

THE INNOVATIVE ESSENCE OF THE PERSONNEL TRAINING SYSTEM AT THE NEW DEVELOPMENT STAGE OF OUR COUNTRY

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Annotation: the article summarizes the main areas of higher education reform in the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on measures for the further development of the higher education system”. In the higher education system, special attention is paid to innovations of the personnel training system. In the context of innovative technologies in the educational process of higher education, innovative activities, innovative approach, the activities and features of the training of cadirs of a higher educational institution are considered.

Keywords: innovative reforms, higher education system, development programs, national model of Personnel Training.

One of the tasks facing the government of our country for the development of economy, social sphere and educational education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, improving the standard of living of the population, is the training of highly qualified personnel. Changes in every field of Republican Life indicate the need to further increase the demand, attention to educated, qualified national personnel, who are receiving education in our country and returning to foreign countries with the improvement of their qualifications. Currently, the attention given to the educational system by our country President Shavkat Mirziyoyev is becoming very large. The higher education system is especially important in this. On April 20, 2017, the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on measures for the further development of the higher education system” was adopted in order to radically improve the higher education system, radically revise the meaning and content of the training of personnel in accordance with the priorities for the socio-economic development of our country, create the necessary conditions for. According to the decision, important tasks of the future comprehensive development of the higher education system were determined. In order to fully ensure an effective solution to the tasks set out in the resolution, a comprehensive development program for the higher education system for 2017-2021 was approved in order to qualitatively increase and radically improve the level of Higher Education, strengthen and modernize the material and technical base of higher education institutions, equip them with modern educational and scientific laboratories, information and communication technologies. In order to further improve the economic system, the radical reform of the system of training of qualified specialists in professional colleges is a period requirement for the application of theoretical, practical, non-traditional methods of education, advanced pedagogical technologies in improving activities for professional orientation in the process of implementing the implementation of the law on education and the” national program of training.

The emergence of innovative technologies is the result of the development of society and the change in requirements. Each new era assumes its own changes and innovations. The goal of new innovative technologies is to increase the effectiveness of education and training at each new stage. Increasing the effectiveness of the educational process makes it possible to move to a new level of quality. In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to develop innovative technologies, that is, new effective manifestations of the progress and organization of the reading process. These innovative technologies should be suitable for the current period, that is, the level of development of a person and the level of development of the technique, and ensure a harmonious combination of human and technical resources. It is from these goals and objectives that the content of innovative technologies will be humanized, individualized, aimed at development, if it is widely considered today. Since the introduction of innovative technologies into the educational process is considered relevant today, our respulikam and foreign educators are taking place on this issue. It should be noted that a number of scientists conducted scientific research on the problems of bringing innovative technologies into the process of teaching Economic Sciences. The introduction of technologies in the educational system that are able to quickly interpret innovations requires a rapid period.

The reforms carried out in our country are aimed at the perfection of the personnel training system, development on the basis of modern economy, science, culture, technology and technologies. Public policy in the field of Personnel Training provides for the formation of a person – citizen who has developed comprehensively through the system of continuing education. This in turn serves to solve the issue of upbringing, training, development of the individual on the basis of science, technology, advanced technologies . In the application of pedagogical technology, however, it is seen that by designing the educational process, the teacher can achieve a high effect, even if he does not have great pedagogical experience. Therefore, it is important to determine the educational goals in the organization of the educational process. Setting specific goals eases control and evaluation work and clarifies the process. In the lesson, it is necessary to create conditions for free, creative work of students. To do this, it will be useful for each part of the lessons to be clearly designed, to adapt the educational material to the levels of assimilation of knowledge holders. The use of interactive methods along with traditional educational methods is one of the important conditions for improving the effectiveness of the lesson. The main emphasis when using interactive techniques is to allow students to work cooperatively. Interactive methods serve to form free thinking, creative abilities in the reader. Today, the use of active teaching methods forms the basis of pedagogical technology. Pedagogical technology is a systematic method of creating, applying and defining the process of teaching and learning, taking into account the resources of the technical and individual and their mutual activities, which sets the task of alternative forms of Education.

Further ensuring the integrity of theory and practice on the results of the analysis, improving the mechanism for monitoring the quality of education, effective cooperation with foreign universities. Thanks to the joint programs implemented, hundreds of teachers and students of Uzbekistan are able to get acquainted with the Advanced International experience in the educational system, acquire new knowledge and skills, improve their skills in the world's leading universities. The high importance of the decision is especially emphasized for the first time at the level of the legislative act of the president of our country when the targeted

development programs, which provide for specific parameters and indicators for each higher education institution, are approved separately. The decision was an important step in improving the educational system of all Uzbekistan. The current stage of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is associated with the implementation of processes of deep reform of the political, economic life, social sphere of society. At the present stage in the Republic, social relations based on the market economy are being formed. The specific model of the transition to market relations is based on taking into account the specific conditions and characteristics of the Republic: traditions, customs, lifestyle. The new conditions of the labor market determined the main directions for the development of the Republican educational system. The law "on education" and the "national program of Personnel Training" provided the necessary legal framework for the consistent development of the educational system as a single Educational, Scientific and production complex on the basis of state educational institutions. The fundamental difference between educational reforms of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the creation of conditions for the gradual development of the system of continuing education, state regulation of the market of educational services and state guarantees for the correct implementation of the quality of Education [2]. The radical reform of the content of education in the Republic necessitated ensuring that the quality of the personnel being prepared meets the requirements of the changes being made in the Republic. From this, state educational standards were established, which were mandatory for all types of educational institutions. The introduction of standards provides for the implementation of the following goals: ensuring high-quality education and training of personnel; democratization, humanization, humanization of the educational process; ensuring continuity and continuity of the educational process and training of personnel; optimization of the educational process in all types and stages of education; ensuring competitiveness in the labor market and educational services. When developing educational standards of the system of continuing education, their compliance with the level of world standards is a decisive factor. Higher education in the Republic occupies a great place in the training of pedagogical personnel and the intellectual elite of the state. In Uzbekistan, the main parameters of the national model of training of Higher Education personnel were determined. The components of the national model of Personnel Training include: personality, State, Society, Continuing Education, Science and production. Uzbekistan today is a fundamentally new state, in which positive changes in all aspects – political, economic, cultural and spiritual-dictate consistent reforms. At each stage of the reforms, innovative technologies are being introduced into the republican system of continuing education, scientific foundations of educational and educational technologies are being developed, pedagogical innovations, author's schools and great experience of new experimental technologies are being studied. Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.

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